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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FAST DISSOLVING TELMISARTAN TABLET BY INCLUSION COMPLEXATION KNEADING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Telmisartan is a potent, long- lasting, nonpeptide antagonist of the angiotensin II type- 1 (AT1) receptor that is indicated for the treatment of essential hypertension. It selectively and insurmountably inhibits stimulation of the AT1 receptor by angiotensin II without affecting other receptor systems involved in cardiovascular regulation. Poor water solubility is the main constant for its oral bioavailability. The rationale of this study to enhance solubility and dissolution of the drug by preparing its complex with β cyclodextrin. In the present study attempt has been made to prepare, formulate and characterize inclusion complex of Telmisartan with β cyclodextrin. The inclusion complex prepared by kneading method. The inclusion complex containing Telmisartan: β cyclodextrin (1:5) was further formulated into fast dissolving tablet by direct compression technique using superdisintegrant like sodium starch glycolate. The prepared complex were characterize using FT-IR, DSC and finally fast dissolving tablet were evaluated for various pharmaceutical characteristics viz. Hardness, % Friability, Weight variation, Wetting time, Drug content and in-vitro dissolution profiles.

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INTRODUCTION

Fast disintegrating or orodispersible tablets (ODTs) are one such novel approach to increase consumer acceptance by virtue of rapid disintegration, self-administration without water or chewing. This delivery system offers convenience for treatment-resistant population who has difficulty in swallowing unit oral dosage form, namely tablets and capsules [1,2]. The demand for these formulations is particularly beneficial to pediatric and geriatric patients. It is estimated that 50 % of the population is affected by dysphagia which results in high incidence of non-compliance and ineffective therapy. To overcome this problem it is necessary to design a formulation which rapidly disperse / dissolve in the oral cavity without the need of water for swallowing. Such dosage form should disintegrate when placed in the mouth and can be swallowed in the liquid form [3,4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material Telmisartan drug was procured from Aristro pharma Pvt Ltd, Mumbai. Sodium starch glycolate and Crosscarmellose sodium from Shreeji chemicals, Mumbai gift sample.

Fast dissolving tablets of Telmisartan were prepared using the complex forming agent β cyclodextrin by kneading method, Sodium starch glycolate, Crosscarmellose sodium use as superdisintegrants, mannitol as sweetening agent, the drug and other ingredients were mixed together by using a glass mortar and pestle, and then passed through sieve no. 60. Then directly compressed by using 7 mm punch of rotary tablet machine.

Pre compression parameters

Angle of repose

Angle of repose was determined using fixed funnel method. The blend was poured through a funnel that can be raised vertically until a maximum cone height (h) was obtained. Radius of the heap (r) was measured and angle of repose was calculated using formula [5]. $\theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$ Where, θ is angle of repose, h is height of pile and r is the radius of the base pile.

Kneading Method

GLI with β -CD in different molar ratios (i.e. 1:5M) were taken. First cyclodextrin is added to the mortar; small quantity of 50% ethanol is added, while triturating to get slurry like consistency. Then slowly drug is incorporated into the slurry and trituration was further continued for one hour. Slurry was then air dried at 25 °C for 24 hours, pulverized and passed through sieve No. 60 and stored in desiccators over fused calcium chloride [6]. By using Telmisartan and β cyclodextrin (1:5M) ratio, it gives better solubility and drug release. Therefore as per the drug to carrier ratio(1:5M), to prepare the formulation which are given table no 1.2 In this 1:5 ratio means 4mg drug & 20mg β Cyclodextrin total weight use is 24mg

Phase Solubility Studies of Pure Drug:

Phase solubility studies of pure drug with different concentrations of β - cyclodextrins (3-15 millimoles) were performed by the method described by Higuchi and Connors. An excess of Telmisartan (200 mg) was added to 15ml of triple distilled water containing various concentrations of cyclodextrins such as 0, 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15 x 10⁻³ moles/liter taken in a series of 25ml stopped conical flask and the mixture was shaken for 72 hours at room temperature on a rotary flask shaker. After 72 hrs of shaking to achieve equilibrium, 2ml aliquots are withdrawn at 1 hr interval and filtered through whatman no.1 filter paper. The filtered samples are diluted suitably and assayed for the drug Telmisartan content by specific UV method. Shaking is continued until the consecutive estimations are the same. The solubility experiments are conducted in triplicate [7-9].

Bulk Density

Apparent bulk density (pb) was determined by pouring blend into a graduated cylinder. The bulk volume (Vb) and weight of powder (M) was determined. The bulk density was calculated using the formula [10]. $pb = M/Vb$

Tapped Density

The measuring cylinder containing known mass of blend was tapped for a fixed time. The minimum volume (Vt) occupied in the cylinder and weight (M) of the blend as measured. The tapped density (ρ_t) was calculated using the formula [4]. $\rho_t = M/Vt$

Carr's compressibility index

The simplex way of measurement of the free flow of powder is compressibility, an indication of the ease with which a material can be induced to flow is given by compressibility index of the granules was determined by Carr's compressibility index (I) which is calculated by using the following formula [11]. $I = \{(V_o - V_t) / V_o\} \times 100$

Hausner ratio

Hausner ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It is calculated by the following

$$\text{Formula Hausner ratio} = \rho_t / \rho_b$$

Where ρ_t is tapped density and ρ_b is bulk density. Lower hausner ratio (< 1.25) indicate better flow properties than higher ones (>1.25).

Post compression parameters

All the batches of tablets were evaluated for various parameters like weight variation, friability, hardness, drug content, disintegration and dissolution and results reported in Table no 1.3

Weight variation test

Twenty tablets were taken and their weight was determined individually and collectively on a digital weighting balance. The average weight of one tablet was determined from the collective weight [12].

Hardness test

The hardness of the tablet was determined using Monsanto Hardness Tester [13].

Friability test

Six tablets from each batch were examined for friability using Roche Friabilator (Tropical Equipment Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India) and the equipment was run for 4min at 25 revolutions per minute. The tablets were taken out, dedusted and reweighted and % friability was calculated [13].

$$\% \text{Friability} = (\text{Loss in weight/Initial weight}) \times 100$$

Water absorption ratio

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was kept in a Petri dish (internal diameter 5.5cm) containing 6ml of purified water. The tablet was placed on the tissue paper and allowed to wet completely. The wetted tablet was removed and reweighted. Water absorption ratio, R was determined according to the following equation [14]. $R = 100 (W_a - W_b)/W_b$ Where W_b and W_a are the weight before and after water absorption, respectively.

Wetting time

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was kept in a Petri dish (inter diameter 5.5cm) containing 6ml of purified water. The tablet was placed on the tissue paper and allowed to wet completely. The time required for complete wetting of the tablet was then recorded.

Uniformity of Content

50 mg of complex was accurately weighed and transferred to 50 ml of volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with methanol. From this 1ml was taken in 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume is adjusted up to the mark with same solvent. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 228 nm. The drug content of Telmisartan was calculated using calibration curve data [15].

In vitro disintegration time

The disintegration test was performed using an USP disintegration apparatus, with distilled water at $24 \pm 0.50^\circ\text{C}$. The time reported to obtain complete disintegration of six tablets were recorded and average was reported

In vitro dissolution testing

Dissolution study was conducted for all the formulation using USP type-II apparatus (Electrolab, Mumbai, In-dia.). The dissolution test was performed using 900 ml of phosphate buffer (PH 7.4) was taken as the dissolution medium at 50 rpm and $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. 10 milliliters of aliquots were periodically withdrawn and the sample volume was replaced with an equal volume of fresh dissolution medium. The samples were analyzed spectrophotometrically at 228nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Physical evaluation of tablets**

All the tablet preparations were evaluated for various physical parameters and content uniformity before proceeding further. Table1.3 includes the values (mean SD) of weight variation, hardness, diameter and thickness of 10 tablet batches prepared using different combinations of functional excipients. Tablet weights in all batches varied between 120.98 to 121.46, thickness between 2.86 mm to 2.95 mm and tablet hardness between 3.18 to 3.59 kg /cm². Thus all the physical parameters of the manually compressed tablets were quite within control. The percentage friability, as depicted in Table1.3 was in the range of 0.550 – 1.03. The tablets of F3 & F9 formulation with low concentration had a friability of more than 1% as compared to tablets of F4 to F10 having a comparatively high medium concentration of superdisintegrant. The reason behind this was that, because of higher percentage subliming ingredient used, the porosity of tablets increased thus giving tablets which were friable. However, for orodispersible tablets the percentage friability up to or slightly above 1% is permissible.

Wetting time:

The wetting time, as shown in Table 1.4 of all ten formulations was in the range of 8 to 15 seconds. The wetting time is closely related to the disintegration time. There is a direct relationship between the wetting time and disintegration time, which is: faster the wetting time, faster is the disintegration time.

Uniformity of Content

The drug content for tablets of all formulations was found to be in the range of 98.23 – 99.90. Thus all formulation batches of Telmisartan found to be contain the drug within the acceptable range [16-17].

Dissolution Studies

In pH 7.4 phosphate buffer

The dissolution studies were carried out on optimum formulations are shown in Figure 1.1, 1.2 The release of drug was largely depended on the disintegration time. That is faster the disintegration of tablets, better and faster is the release. F6 of SSG releases 95.19% of drug after 60 min. while F10 of CCS showed 99.27 % release after 60 minutes. Hence, CCS showed most efficient drug release than SSG formulation in 7.4 phosphate buffer [18].

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

The thermal behavior Telmisartan - β -CD complex was studied using DSC in order to confirm the formation of complex. DSC thermogram of Telmisartan and β CD formulation is shown in fig. 7.13 and 7.14 respectively. The DSC thermogram of Telmisartan showed an endothermic peak at 214°C corresponding to its melting point. The thermogram of β CD showed endothermic peak at 114°C which is different from the pure drug, which gives clear evidence that there is formation of the complex [19-21]

Table 1. Formulation by kneading method.

Method	Drug to Carrier Complex	Drug to Carrier Ratio	% Release
Kneading Method	Telmisartan: β cyclodextrin	1:1	91.01 \pm 0.32
	Telmisartan: β cyclodextrin	1:2	95.27 \pm 0.33
	Telmisartan: β cyclodextrin	1:5	99.45 \pm 0.31

Table 2. Formulation of Ten batches for 1:5 complex formation.

Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Telmisartan + β Cyclodextrin (mg)	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24
Microcrystalline Cellulose(mg)	11	10	9	11	10	9	11	10	9	11
Lactose (mg)	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58
Mannitol (mg)	qs									
Sodium Starch Glycolate (mg)	2	4	6	8	10	--	--	--	--	--
Crosscarmellose Sodium (mg)	--	--	---	---	---	2	4	6	8	10
Aerosil (mg)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Magnesium Stearate (mg)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Total (mg)	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

Table 3. Physical Evaluation of Tablets Prepared by using β cyclodextrins.

Batch	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Weight Variation	% Friability
F1	2.91 \pm 0.045	3.59 \pm 0.31	120.54 \pm 0.43	0.703 \pm 0.21
F2	2.96 \pm 0.035	3.51 \pm 0.29	121.25 \pm 0.70	0.687 \pm 0.33
F3	2.93 \pm 0.040	3.54 \pm 0.56	120.50 \pm 0.50	1.03 \pm 0.30
F4	2.95 \pm 0.090	3.45 \pm 0.11	121.46 \pm 0.44	0.549 \pm 0.56
F5	2.89 \pm 0.080	3.35 \pm 0.37	120.77 \pm 0.81	0.674 \pm 0.64
F6	2.92 \pm 0.032	3.49 \pm 0.40	120.69 \pm 0.92	1.01 \pm 0.51
F7	2.90 \pm 0.075	3.35 \pm 0.49	121.10 \pm 0.85	0.550 \pm 0.36
F8	2.86 \pm 0.050	3.33 \pm 0.52	121.15 \pm 0.35	0.575 \pm 0.35
F9	2.87 \pm 0.043	3.27 \pm 0.22	121.13 \pm 0.77	1.03 \pm 0.33
F10	2.92 \pm 0.036	3.15 \pm 0.51	119.87 \pm 0.35	0.527 \pm 0.32

Table 4. Values of Disintegration time, Wetting time, Water absorption ratio and Uniformity of content orodispersible tablet formulation of Telmisartan prepared employing complexation technique (F1-F10). (n = 3).

Batch	Disintegration Time (Sec)	Wetting Time (Sec)	Water Absorption Ratio	Uniformity of Content
F1	14 ± 1.33	13±1.14	96.03 ± 0.044	98.72± 0.60
F2	13± 0.5	12±1.673	94.02± 0.046	98.23± 0.48
F3	10± 0.5	11 ± 2.00	91.91± 0.058	99.34± 0.62
F4	15± 0.2	14±1.483	97.95± 0.029	98.99±0.60
F5	14± 0.60	13± 1.580	97.94±0.031	98.72± 0.83
F6	13± 0.60	12± 1.571	91.95±0.023	98.59± 0.52
F7	11± 0.07	10±2.236	94.14±0.019	98.21± 0.52
F8	10± 0.05	9±3.050	95.60±0.047	99.20±0.70
F9	15± 0.07	14±1.344	87.15± 0.073	98.92± 0.87
F10	9± 0.05	8±1.673	98.98± 0.086	99.93± 0.30

Table 5. Results of In-vitro Dissolution Study of F1-F5 Formulation.

Time (min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	12.43±0.37	14.44±0.30	16.23±0.44	13.72±0.33	11.93±0.44
10	28.55±0.34	29.05±0.45	28.58±0.41	28.53±0.34	27.97±0.33
15	35.38±0.35	36.97±0.33	38.27±0.45	35.43±0.45	34.34±0.44
20	40.12±0.36	44.46±0.48	40.99±0.34	41.90±0.34	42.29±0.32
25	45.55±0.31	48.25±0.46	48.05±0.45	48.44±0.45	48.06±0.34
30	55.00±0.33	62.20±0.47	60.70±0.33	62.38±0.44	53.12±0.45
35	65.44±0.41	68.70±0.44	64.42±0.55	67.11±0.33	64.30±0.34
40	70.45±0.38	72.49±0.49	72.21±0.34	70.64±0.33	72.56±0.44
45	78.58±0.39	75.82±0.40	75.52±0.44	75.45±0.44	77.88±0.43
50	82.48±0.41	80.69±0.48	82.40±0.55	80.81±0.45	84.00±0.42
55	88.71±0.43	84.84±0.43	86.31±0.34	82.94±0.33	89.43±0.43
60	92.19±0.44	89.28±0.50	92.77±0.44	88.62±0.44	94.15±0.34

Table 6. Results of In-vitro Dissolution Study of F6-F10 Formulation.

Time (min)	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	13.45±0.34	16.48±0.33	17.23±0.44	15.72±0.44	16.48±0.33
10	29.50±0.32	31.05±0.34	32.58±0.43	29.53±0.43	31.81±0.32
15	37.40±0.32	38.97±0.33	41.27±0.34	37.43±0.34	39.74±0.31
20	43.12±0.34	45.46±0.44	43.99±0.44	43.90±0.31	44.72±0.34
25	49.65±0.31	51.25±0.42	52.05±0.43	50.44±0.30	53.54±0.35
30	57.00±0.33	66.20±0.41	61.70±0.31	65.38±0.44	60.93±0.36
35	67.46±0.43	70.70±0.34	68.42±0.30	69.11±0.34	69.16±0.33
40	73.49±0.31	74.49±0.32	75.21±0.33	73.64±0.42	75.96±0.43
45	82.60±0.44	79.82±0.43	77.52±0.42	77.45±0.41	85.10±0.41
50	86.50±0.41	83.69±0.42	84.40±0.33	82.81±0.44	88.27±0.44
55	92.71±0.43	86.84±0.45	88.31±0.43	85.94±0.33	94.50±0.33
60	95.19±0.43	92.28±0.40	93.77±0.42	90.62±0.33	99.27±0.34

Figure 1. Dissolution Profile of F1-F5 Formulation

CONCLUSION

The Cyclodextrins like β -CD can be used to prepare inclusion complexes of Telmisartan with improved solubility of the drug by kneading method. Telmisartan formed inclusion complexes with β -CD in 1:5 M ratio shows highest solubility and dissolution rate. The inclusion complex prepared with β -CD by kneading method formulation (F10) showed highest solubility and enhancement in dissolution profile by increasing concentration of CCS. Future scope of FDT's Fast Dissolving Tablets can offer several biopharmaceutical advantages such as improve deficiency over conventional dosage forms. For example, they require smaller amount of active ingredient to be effective, improve absorption profiles and offer better drug bioavailability than regular tablets and capsules. In addition FDT's may be suitable for oral delivery of drugs such as protein and peptide based therapeutics that has limited bioavailability when administered by conventional tablets. These products usually degrade rapidly in stomach. Because drugs delivered in FDT's may be absorbed in the pregastric sites of highly permeable buccal and mucosal tissues of oral cavity, they may be suitable for delivering relatively lowmolecular weight and highly permeable drugs. Future possibilities for improvements in FDT's and drug delivery are bright but technology is still relatively new. Several drug delivery technologies that can be leveraged on improving drug therapy from FDT's have yet to be fully realized.

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